

THE APPLICATION OF THE MODEL CORRECTION FACTOR METHOD TO A RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF A COMPOSITE BLADE STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY

This paper presents a reliability analysis of a composite blade profile. The so-called Model Correction Factor technique is applied as an effective alternate approach to the response surface technique. The structural reliability is determined by use of a simplified idealised analytical model which in a probabilistic sense is model corrected so that it close to the design point represents the same structural behaviour as a realistic FE model.

Keywords: Reliability Modelling, Structural Safety, Model Correction Factor, Composite Failure

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that properties of composite materials may exhibit significant uncertainty depending on the type of material systems applied, manufacturing techniques, fabrication quality, etc. This uncertainty as well as the uncertainty in the loading will influence the reliability of the composite structure. It is thus important to be able to analyze both the reliability of the structure and to get insight into the variability of the structural response, given statistical variation of both the materials applied and the loading the structure is exposed to.

Whether using Monte Carlo simulations or FORM/SORM techniques the reliability analysis of any engineering structure will always involve several evaluations of the limit state function that describes the failure mode of the structure. For many engineering problems the structural analysis requires detailed use of nonlinear finite-element analysis. Such analyses will almost always become so time consuming that this militates against its use as an integrated part of the reliability analysis. For that reason the application of the response surface techniques has been widely applied. In the response surface technique the structural response is approximated by fitting a polynomial surface, typically quadratic, and the response surface is typically adaptively

adjusted through the analysis, cf. Bucher & Bourgund 1990 [1]. The technique has proven to be reliable and precise and (together with the Monte Carlo analysis or FORM/SORM techniques) it has found its application to a wide range of engineering problems.

Even a simple response surface technique may require a considerable number of complex and time consuming finite element analyses. In this study reliability analysis of a blade structure is presented, where the number of calls to the high-complexity finite element model have been minimised by the application of the so-called Model Correction Factor method (Ditlevsen & Arnbjerg-Nielsen 1994 [2]). The Model Correction Factor method makes use of a simplified analytical model (for example a beam model) that captures part of the structural behaviour. This model is then, in a probabilistic sense, calibrated to the complex finite element model.

The paper illustrates the application of the Model Correction Factor to a cantilever structure with an aerodynamic blade profile, consisting of a glass-fiber-reinforced polymer composite material and subjected to out-of-plane bending.

2. METHODS

Model Correction Factor Method

The Model Correction Factor (Ditlevsen & Arnbjerg-Nielsen, 1994 [2]) represents a powerful alternative to the traditional response surface technique, where a simple, idealised analytical model, in a probabilistic sense, is calibrated to a complex but realistic finite element model so that the simple model predicts the same response as the realistic model, at least in the vicinity of the calibration point.

Let the probabilistic structural resistance of the realistic model be designated as $R^{REAL}(\mathbf{X})$, where \mathbf{X} is a vector of stochastic input variables. In a similar manner the resistance of the idealistic model at the same point \mathbf{X} may be defined as $R^{IDEAL}(\mathbf{X})$. Then a function $\nu(\mathbf{X})$ exists, such that

$$R^{REAL}(\mathbf{X}) = \nu(\mathbf{X}) \cdot R^{IDEAL}(\mathbf{X}) \quad (1)$$

Equation $R^{REAL}(\mathbf{X}) = \nu(\mathbf{X}) \cdot R^{IDEAL}(\mathbf{X})$ (1) will always hold true, however determining the entire function $\nu(\mathbf{X})$ will be even more complicated and time-consuming than evaluating $R^{REAL}(\mathbf{X})$. Therefore Ditlevsen and Arnbjerg-Nielsen (1994 [1]) suggested to approximate $\nu(\mathbf{X})$ by its zero- or first-order Taylor series expansion around the design point of the simplified model. This approach can be justified, because the selected simplified model captures part of the same physical behaviour of the structure as the realistic model does. Using a zero- or first-order approximation around the design point for the idealised model \mathbf{X}^* will in most cases give sufficiently precise approximation. The application of a second or higher-order approximation might be beneficial in terms of accuracy. However, the gain in accuracy may not justify the increase of computational efforts required to obtain the higher-order approximation.

The reliability of the realistic model is determined in a sequence of iterations, where during each successive step a design point is obtained by reliability analysis of the

simplified model, and then the model correction factor, $\nu(\mathbf{X})$, is updated by assuring that equation (1) holds to zero or first order in the vicinity of the new design point.

The procedure can be summarised by the following steps:

- 1) Perform an initial iteration $i = 0$. Initialise $\nu(\mathbf{X})$ by solving eq. (1) at the mean values $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{X})$.
- 2) $i = i + 1$. Obtain the design point \mathbf{X}_i^* by performing reliability analysis of the idealised model.
- 3) Determine the realistic response $R^{REAL}(\mathbf{X}_i^*)$ at the newly obtained design point.
- 4) Solve (1) for the design point \mathbf{X}_i^* and obtain an updated value of the model correction factor $\nu^i(\mathbf{X}_i^*)$.
- 5) Has the series of design points converged? If not, go back to step 2
- 6) If the series of design points has converged, the reliability of the realistic model can be approximated by the reliability found using the simplified model obtained at the final design point.

It should be noted that convergence to the correct design point is not assured.

Typically the model correction factor algorithm achieves very fast convergence (3-6 iterations). If a zero-order approximation of the model correction factor is used, the realistic model is called once for each iteration step. When a first-order approximation is used the partial derivatives for each input variable have to be determined, and therefore the calls to the realistic model for each iteration equals the size of the vector $\mathbf{X} + 1$. This shows how the computational efficiency sharply decreases with increasing order of the Taylor series approximation.

Due to the gains in computational efficiency the zero-order approximation of $\nu(\mathbf{X})$ is usually desirable, and if the physics of the simplified model are sufficiently close to the physics of the realistic model, a zero-order approximation should give sufficiently accurate results.

Quite often however, due to its simplicity, the idealistic model will lack some of the physics of the realistic model, and will therefore be unable to take some of the input parameters into consideration. In such cases the use of a first-order approximation for $\nu(\mathbf{X})$ is necessary, as this approximation allows for the model correction factor to take into account the effect of variables not influencing the simplified model.

Composite modelling: Classical Lamination Theory and Tsai-Wu Failure Criterion

A simple and widely used approach for analysis of layered composite materials is the Classical Lamination Theory (CLT). In CLT the composite material is considered as a stacked sequence of transversely isotropic layers (laminas). CLT and the transversely isotropic assumption facilitates a good approximation for most layered fibre polymer materials, since the transverse directions are perpendicular to the fibre direction, and the transverse properties are primarily governed by the matrix properties. In the fibre

direction (1) most of the load is carried by the fibres and the stiffness and strength are dominated by the fibre properties.

The application of CLT to a laminated composite results in estimates of the laminate's global stiffness, as well as estimates of the layer-wise stresses and strains. The failure behaviour of the laminate can be estimated by the application of a composite failure criterion.

The failure state of the idealised model used in this paper is assessed through the application of a last-ply failure algorithm, where the Tsai-Wu failure criterion is integrated within CLT.

3. THE PROBLEM

In this study the reliability against failure of a GFRP composite blade structure consisting of a stacked sequence of angled unidirectional layers is determined by use of the Model Correction Factor method integrated with analytical and finite element based structural analysis based on classical laminate theory.

The blade cross section is uniform along the entire length of the blade and is shown on Figure 1.

Figure 1 Cross section of the blade profile

The structure is subjected to a dead gravity load in the form of a bulb mass m . The blade is inclined at angle θ to the vertical, which results in both axial force F_x and an out-of-plane bending force F_z , as shown schematically on Figure 2:

Figure 2 Schematic representation of blade structure

The centre of gravity of the bulb mass lies on the blade x -axis, therefore it is considered that the bulb weight does not cause any moment about the x -axis.

Simplified model

In the simplified model the blade profile is represented analytically as a cantilever Euler-Bernoulli beam.

The normal stresses in the beam cross section are determined by:

$$\sigma_x = \frac{F_x}{A} + \frac{M_y \cdot z}{I_{yy}} \quad (2)$$

Where

$M_y = F_z(L - x)$ is the internal moment about the beam y -axis;

$A = S \cdot t$ is the area covered by the beam cross section;

F_x is the axial force;

z is an arbitrary out-of plane location on the beam cross section

I_{yy} is the beam cross section area moment of inertia about the y -axis

The moment of inertia of the cross section is derived numerically using the general geometric expression

$$I_{yy} = \int z^2 dA \quad (3)$$

The blade cross section is divided along its height into a large number of areas with width, equal to the width of the cross section and with infinitesimal height, see Figure 3. Each of these areas can then be considered as approximately rectangular, thus their

surface areas can be estimated, facilitating a possibility to approximate the area moment of inertia by evaluating the integral in equation (3) numerically.

Figure 3 Numerical derivation of area moment of inertia

The scheme illustrated in Figure 3 shows how the infinitesimal areas dA_i are derived for a solid cross section. For a hollow cross section, as the blade profile considered in this section, the expression for dA_i is modified to

$$dA_i = dA_{i,outer} - dA_{i,inner} = b_i \cdot 0.5 \cdot \left((a_i^{outer} + a_{i+1}^{outer}) - (a_i^{inner} - a_{i+1}^{inner}) \right) \quad (4)$$

Where a_i^{inner} and a_i^{outer} are respectively the inner width (the distance between the inner faces) and the outer width (the distance between the outer faces) of the cross section. The integral in Equation (3) is evaluated numerically by

$$I_{yy} = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} z_i^2 \cdot dA_i \quad (5)$$

The stress evaluation given by equation (2) is only an approximation as it assumes linear variation of stresses across the shell thickness. For a laminated composite with varying ply angles the stress does not vary linearly due to the directionality of layer stiffness properties. Therefore equation (2) cannot be used to obtain local lamina stresses. However, the numerical algorithm is applied to estimate the averaged resulting distribution of σ_x , which can then subsequently be integrated to achieve the internal forces \mathbf{N} and internal moments \mathbf{M} :

$$N_i = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_i . dz \quad , i = x, y, xy ; M_i = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_i . z . dz \quad , i = x, y, xy \quad (6)$$

The laminate internal forces and moments are then applied in the CLT to obtain the local stress and strain distributions across the local shell thickness.

Two critical locations are identified - the top and the bottom of the profile height, where under the current loading the stresses reach their maximum. The stresses in these two locations are considered as the design-drivers for the current problem, and if failure occurs at any of these points, then the structure is regarded as failed.

The limit state is obtained by gradually increasing the load (the bulb mass, m) and evaluating the Tsai-Wu failure criterion for the top and bottom of each layer at the critical points. If the failure criterion for any of the layers identifies failure, the stiffness of this layer is reduced to a negligibly small value. The analysis continues until all layers in at least one critical point have failed.

The approach described above does not take into account any material or geometric coupling effects such as for example bend-twist couplings. This is a necessary simplification, as the “idealised” model used in the Model Correction Factor analysis has to be simple and computationally fast. The idealised model does not necessarily have to account for all possible physical phenomena in the real structure, as the theoretical nature of the Model Correction Factor technique is that the simplified model approximates only the most important physical parameters of the real structure. The correlation of the behaviour between the idealised and real structure is ensured by the probabilistic “tuning” described above.

Realistic model

The realistic model of the structure is a nonlinear shell-element model generated in the commercial finite element (FE) code, ANSYS. An automated script performs stepwise nonlinear analysis. At each load step the stresses at the two critical points identified in the simplified model are extracted from the model, and the Tsai-Wu failure criterion is evaluated. Similarly to the simplified model, in case of layer failure, the stiffness of the layer is reduced to a negligible value, and the analysis is continued until all layers in at least one critical point have failed.

The blade profile is represented by a surface consisting of approximately 2000 shell elements, see Figure 4. The bulb weight is represented by a concentrated force in a downward direction, applied at a single master node at the location of the bulb centre of gravity. The master node is connected to the slave nodes on the tip of the blade profile using multi-point constraint (MPC) equations.

The ultimate failure capacity of the model is evaluated by performing a series of static nonlinear structural analyses. After each analysis step the Tsai-Wu failure criterion is evaluated for the top and the bottom of each layer. If for any layer the criterion shows failure, the stiffness of the layer is reduced to a very small value. Then the load is stepped up and a new analysis step is carried out. Each analysis step is defined as an analysis restart, i.e. the solver continues the solution from the last converged load step,

and is seeking a new equilibrium after the update of the applied forces and layer stiffnesses.

Figure 4 Finite element model of blade profile, ANSYS

Input Parameters

The input to the problem includes both deterministic and stochastic parameters. The geometry of the blade profile is defined as deterministic (no variance) and has the following dimensions:

Blade length, $L = 6\text{m}$

Blade profile width, $b = 0.45\text{m}$

Blade profile height, $z = 0.15\text{m}$

Where the height, z , is the distance between the two outermost points on the blade shell profile, as shown on Figure 1.

Eleven parameters are input as stochastic, including the load (the bulb mass), shell thickness, the elastic moduli, and the strength parameters of the UD plies. Table 1 gives an overview of the uncertainty modelling of the stochastic inputs:

Table 1 List of stochastic input parameters

#	Parameters, X		μ	CoV
1	Bulb Mass	m [kg]	1500	5%
2	Shell thickness	t_{face} [m]	0.012	10%
3	Longitudinal modulus	E_1 [Pa]	$54 \cdot 10^9$	7%
4	Transverse modulus	E_2 [Pa]	$18 \cdot 10^9$	7%

5	Shear modulus	G_{12} [Pa]	9.10^9	7%
6	Poisson ratio	PR_{12} [-]	0.25	7%
7	Tensile strength, fibre dir.	X_t [Pa]	1035.10^6	12%
8	Compressive strength, fibre dir.	X_c [Pa]	-1035.10^6	12%
9	Tensile strength, transverse	Y_t [Pa]	28.10^6	12%
10	Compressive strength, transverse	Y_c [MPa]	-138.10^6	18%
11	Shear strength	S [MPa]	41.10^6	25%

All parameters are assumed to have lognormal distribution.

The parameter “shell thickness” defines the total thickness of the layered-composite outer shell of the blade profile. It is assumed constant over the entire cross section of the blade.

The laminate layup consists of 12 layers with the following orientation angles θ :

$$\theta_{mean} = [-45^\circ \quad 45^\circ \quad 0^\circ \quad -45^\circ \quad 45^\circ \quad 0^\circ \quad -45^\circ \quad 45^\circ \quad 0^\circ] \quad (7)$$

All layers are considered to have equal thickness, or $1/12^{\text{th}}$ of the outer shell thickness. The triax combination of -45, 45 and 0 degree laminas is chosen to represent a typical layup, commonly used in composite structures, and has more uniform stiffness (less directionality) compared to a pure unidirectional layup.

The coefficients of variation of the elastic moduli and the material strength properties are defined according to the results of Branner (1994) [3]. The coefficients of variation of the bulb mass and face thickness are subjectively chosen.

The stochastic variables are considered to be completely uncorrelated, i.e. the distributions of all parameters are considered independent of each other.

First-order Taylor series expansion

The formulation of the simplified model results in an estimation of the failure capacity of the structure using the stress-based Tsai-Wu failure criterion. The use of a stress-based criterion in combination with CLT means that the elastic properties of the material will only have a second-order effect on the simplified model. Therefore using a zero-order Taylor approximation of the Model Correction Factor will render the analysis practically insensitive to the variation in the material elastic moduli. Implementing a first order Taylor series expansion around a design point \mathbf{X}^* means that the slope (partial derivatives) of the model correction factor will be taken into account for each variable in \mathbf{X}^* . Thus the effect of the elastic moduli on the model correction factor and on the structural reliability will be taken into account through the realistic model, which is used to determine the partial derivatives, and which is sensitive to changes in the material elastic properties.

The first-order approximation of the model correction factor is established by finding the partial derivatives of $\nu(\mathbf{X})$ with respect to each of the parameters in \mathbf{X} . For example the partial derivative of $\nu(\mathbf{X})$ with respect to the bulb mass is evaluated numerically in the following way:

$$\frac{\partial v(\mathbf{X})}{\partial m} \approx \frac{v(\bar{\mathbf{X}}^m, m + \Delta m) - v(\bar{\mathbf{X}}^m, m)}{\Delta m} = \left(\frac{R^{REAL}(\bar{\mathbf{X}}^m, m + \Delta m)}{R^{IDEAL}(\bar{\mathbf{X}}^m, m + \Delta m)} - \frac{R^{REAL}(\bar{\mathbf{X}}^m, m)}{R^{IDEAL}(\bar{\mathbf{X}}^m, m)} \right) / \Delta m \quad (8)$$

Where $\bar{\mathbf{X}}^m$ is the vector of input variables except m . The differential mass dm equals 0.5% of the mean value of the bulb mass m . The same value of 0.5% is also used for all other parameters, therefore $d\mathbf{X} = 0.005 \cdot \mathbf{X}$.

Finally, the first-order Taylor series expansion of the model correction factor is obtained by:

$$v(\mathbf{X}) \approx v(\mathbf{X}_0) + (\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_0) Dv(\mathbf{X}_0) \quad (9)$$

Where $Dv(\mathbf{X}_0)$ is the gradient of $v(\mathbf{X})$ evaluated at \mathbf{X}_0 using the method given in equation (8).

4. RESULTS

Zero order Taylor expansion

Table 2 presents the results for a reliability analysis with the model correction factor approximated as a zero order Taylor series expansion.

Table 2 Results from reliability analysis of a blade structure using MCF method, zero-order Taylor approximation

#	X^*	Iteration number					
		$l = 0$	$l = 1$	$l = 2$	$l = 3$	$l = 4$	$l = 5$
1	m [kg]	2000	2052.3	2029.7	2035.5	2031.2	2033.7
2	t_{face} [m]	0.012	0.01053	0.01109	0.01094	0.01105	0.01099
3	E_t [Pa]	54.10^9	$53.9.10^9$	$53.9.10^9$	$53.9.10^9$	$53.9.10^9$	$5.39E+10$
4	E_2 [Pa]	18.10^9	$17.9.10^9$	$17.9.10^9$	$17.9.10^9$	$17.9.10^9$	$1.80E+10$
5	G_{I2} [Pa]	9.10^9	$8.98.10^9$	$8.98.10^9$	$8.98.10^9$	$8.98.10^9$	$8.98E+09$
6	PR_{I2} [-]	0.25	0.249	0.249	0.249	0.249	$2.49E-01$
7	X_t [Pa]	1035.10^6	877.10^6	936.10^6	921.10^6	932.10^6	$9.26E+08$
8	X_c [Pa]	-1035.10^6	-1028.10^6	-1028.10^6	-1028.10^6	-1028.10^6	$-1.03E+09$
9	Y_t [Pa]	28.10^6	$27.8.10^6$	$27.8.10^6$	$27.8.10^6$	$27.8.10^6$	$2.78E+07$
10	Y_c [MPa]	-138.10^6	-137.10^6	-137.10^6	-137.10^6	-137.10^6	$-1.37E+08$
11	S [MPa]	41.10^6	$39.8.10^6$	$39.8.10^6$	$39.8.10^6$	$39.8.10^6$	$3.98E+07$
	$R^{REAL} / (v_0(i-1).R^{IDEAL})$		0.715	1.036	0.974	1.015	0.997
	β		1.910	1.122	1.325	1.173	1.2604
	$P_{failure}$		$6.44.10^{-2}$	$2.13.10^{-1}$	$1.66.10^{-1}$	$2.01.10^{-1}$	$1.8.10^{-1}$
	v_0	0.8189	0.7150	0.7405	0.7214	0.7323	0.7305

First order Taylor expansion

Table 3 presents the results for a reliability analysis with the model correction factor approximated as a first order Taylor series expansion. The expansion is performed using the method, described in Chapter 2 of this paper.

Table 3 Results from reliability analysis of a blade structure using MCF method, first-order Taylor approximation

#	χ^*	Iteration number				
		l = 0	l = 1	l = 2	...	l = 6
1	m [kg]	2000	2020.4	2013.4	...	2024.9
2	t_{face} [m]	0.012	0.011168	0.011418	...	0.011691
3	E_1 [Pa]	54.10^9	$53.1.10^9$	$53.3.10^9$...	$53.6.10^9$
4	E_2 [Pa]	18.10^9	$18.3.10^9$	$18.1.10^9$...	$18.4.10^9$
5	G_{12} [Pa]	9.10^9	$8.93.10^9$	$8.95.10^9$...	$8.96.10^9$
6	PR_{12} [-]	0.25	0.25529	0.25601	...	0.25568
7	X_t [Pa]	1035.10^6	926.10^6	1025.10^6	...	995.10^6
8	X_c [Pa]	-1035.10^6	-1045.10^6	-1034.10^6	...	-1127.10^6
9	Y_t [Pa]	28.10^6	$25.7.10^6$	$27.7.10^6$...	$27.2.10^6$
10	Y_c [MPa]	-138.10^6	$-137.8.10^6$	$-137.4.10^6$...	$-137.2.10^6$
11	S [MPa]	41.10^6	$39.5.10^6$	$39.5.10^6$...	$39.6.10^6$
	$\frac{R^{REAL}}{\left(\nu_0(i-1).R^{IDEAL}\right)}$		0.8298	1.1349	...	0.980
	β		1.386	0.650	...	1.040
	$P_{failure}$		$1.53.10^{-1}$	$3.23.10^{-1}$...	$2.32.10^{-1}$
	ν_0	0.8189	0.6795	0.7712	...	0.6717

5. DISCUSSION

Reliability against ultimate failure of a composite blade structure

For illustrative reasons the reliability analysis of the composite blade structure was performed using both a zero-order and a first-order Taylor series expansion. In both cases fast convergence was found. Using the zero-order approximation of the model correction factor method required only 5 iterations and thus only 5 function calls to the advanced non-linear finite element model. The procedure using the first order expansion converged after 6 iterations, however 12 calls to the realistic model were required in each iteration (one at the design point and one additional call for each of the stochastic variables in order the partial derivatives to be determined). Therefore using the first-order Taylor series expansion has led to approximately 12 times increase in computational efforts for each iteration.

The results for the zero- and first-order analyses show similar tendencies for the most important parameters - the tensile strength, the bulb mass, and the shell thickness. The resulting reliability index β however is not the same, showing that expanding the model correction factor from its 0th to its 1st-order approximation has introduced new information to the analysis, and using purely zero-order Model Correction Factor is not sufficient.

Buckling

Face buckling is one of the most common failure modes for blade structures. The blade profile used in this study is chosen such that the ultimate failure capacity is governed by material ultimate strength, and not buckling. However, for a profile with a different geometry buckling might be the predominant failure mode.

In order for the reliability analysis to be valid and the obtained reliability index to be correct, the failure modes of the realistic and the simplified models have to be the same at the design point. Since the simplified analytical model used in this paper does not take buckling into account, it can only be used in cases where the failure mode at the design point is due to material failure caused by global bending. A further complication to the analysis might occur if the failure modes at the design point and at the origin (mean values of all parameters) are different. Change of failure modes of the realistic model between the iterative steps will cause discontinuity of the response of the realistic model and will complicate the convergence of the analysis.

This limitation of the simplified model suggests a possible future expansion of the current setup by implementing a simplified model which is capable of taking buckling into account, for example a plastic hinge model, as used in Garre et al. (2006) [3], but modified for application of composite materials with typically brittle failure behaviour.

Importance factors

The importance factors are a result of the reliability analysis that identifies the sensitivity of the solution to changes in each of the input parameters. Higher importance factor for a given parameter would mean that the variation of this parameter has a greater influence on the structural reliability. In the present analysis the highest importance factors are obtained for the laminate face thickness and the tensile strength in the fibre direction, implying that these two parameters are the ones that have the highest influence on the ultimate failure capacity of the composite structure, analysed in the present study.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper the reliability of a composite blade structure is evaluated using the Model Correction Factor Method. A simplified Bernoulli-Euler beam model is in a probabilistic sense calibrated to a detailed nonlinear finite-element model so that at a certain design point the simplified model has the same reliability as the detailed model. This approach leads to considerable improvement of computational efficiency over classical response surface methods, because the numerically “cheap” idealistic model is

used as the response surface, while the time-consuming detailed model is called only a few times until the simplified model is calibrated to the detailed model. The iterative procedure results in a fast convergence and the solution is obtained only after a few iterations.

The Model Correction Factor procedure performs efficiently because the simplified model behaves similarly to the realistic model, capturing the most important physical phenomena leading to ultimate failure. A number of factors such as geometric nonlinearity are not considered in the simplified model and therefore it cannot be completely accurate, but by the application of the Model Correction Factor, the simplified model is tuned to correspond to the realistic model around the design point.

The computational efficiency of the Model Correction Factor method greatly depends on the order of the Taylor-series expansion used. The computational efforts for obtaining a solution with first-order expansion compared to a zero-order expansion multiply with a factor, equal to one plus the number of stochastic variables in the analysis (in the present case the first-order expansion with 11 independent stochastic parameters leads to a 12-fold increase in computational efforts). Therefore the use of a first-order expansion for a given stochastic parameter is justified only in case the zero-order approximation will not yield sufficient accuracy because the idealistic model is not able to catch the influence of this parameter. Such a case is demonstrated in the present paper, where the idealistic model does not capture the influence of the material elastic moduli. At the same time the model captures the influence of the most critical parameters to a reasonable degree, and therefore the use of zero-order approximation for these parameters should in most cases be sufficient. A first-order approximation of the Model Correction Factor is required for the remaining parameters, the influence of which cannot be taken into account by the idealistic model.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been performed within the context of the Network of Excellence on Marine Structures (MARSTRUCT) partially funded by the European Union through the Growth Programme under contract TNE3-CT-2003-506141.

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